

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: KEY CONCEPTS, CORE PRINCIPLES, AND THE CRITICAL NEEDS FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management is a process, which consists of four main activities, namely, acquisition, development, motivation, as well as maintenance of human resources. According to Edwin B. Flippo, - Human resource management is the planning, organizing, directing and controlling of the procurement, development, resources to the end that individual and societal objectives are accomplished. This definition reveals that human resource (HR) management is that aspect of management, which deals with the planning, organizing, directing and controlling the personnel functions of the enterprise. Human Resource Management is responsible for maintaining good human relations in the organization. It is also concerned with development of individuals and achieving integration of goals of the organization and those of the individuals so here, we give our focus on every issue of human resource management. The first and foremost work by the HR is to develop sound organizational structure with strong interpersonal skill to employees, and also to train employees by introducing them the concept of globalize human resource management to perform better in the global organizational context. All the issues and challenges like, work force diversity, leadership development, change management, organizational effectiveness, globalization, E-Commerce, succession planning and compensation etc. can be best management by HR manager when they will work with HR practices, such as rigid recruitment and selection policy, division of jobs, empowerment, encouraging diversity in the workplace, training and development of the workforce, fostering innovation, proper assignment of duties and responsibilities, managing knowledge and other functions, as are shown. Nutshell when HR works enthusiastically by keeping all the practices in minds, competitive advantages can thus be accomplished, the value of human resources can be improved, organization efficiency can be enhanced, and the organization will sustain to survive.

Keywords: HRM, Concepts of HRM, Purpose of HRM, Organizational Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations are made up of people and function through people. Without people organization cannot exist. The resources of men, money, materials and machinery are collected, coordinated and utilized through people. These resources by themselves cannot fulfil the objectives of an organization. They need to be united into a team. It is through the combined effort of people that material and monetary resources are effectively utilized for attainment of common objectives. Without united human effort, no organization can achieve its goals. All the activities of an organization are initiated and completed by the persons who make up the organization. Therefore, people are the most significant resources of any organization. This resource is called human resource and it is the most important factor of production. According to L. F. Urwick, "Business houses are made or broken in the long run not by markets or capital, patents or equipment but by men." Of all the resources manpower is the only resource which does not depreciate, with the passage of time.

From the national viewpoint, human resources may be defined as "the knowledge, skills, creative abilities, talents and aptitude obtained in the population." From the viewpoint of an organization, human resources represent the people at work. They are the sum total of the inherent abilities, acquired knowledge and skills as exemplified in the talents and aptitudes of its employees. According to Michael J. Jucius, human resources or human factors refer to "a whole consisting of inter-related, inter-dependent and interacting physiological, psychological, sociological and ethical components." Thus, human resources represent the quantitative and qualitative measurement of the workforce required in an organization.

The overall aim of modern human resource management is to ensure that the organization is able to achieve its objectives through its staff. In order to reach its objectives an organization needs not only qualified staff but also effective and efficient systems as well as access to and effective allocation of financial resources. Institutional development therefore involves not only putting the right person at the right place at the right time, but also that the organization provides a conducive and effective work environment and systems and that the organization has access to adequate financial resources. In addition to human resources, the organization needs systems like computers and financial management system, transport to reach the client, medicines in a hospital, books in the school, etc. Top management must reach a harmonious balance between all such resources and push and pull factors. HRM should develop objectives

for its activities linked to the overall objectives of the organization. The purpose of development of HRM objectives is to provide a direction for the HRM activities in an often-turbulent environment so that, on the one hand, the business needs of the organization, and, on the other hand the individual and collective needs of its employees can be met by the development and implementation of understandable and effective HR policies and practices. HR policies and practices are linked to the HRM strategy. An HRM strategy is mostly an attitude of mind, a belief in the advantages in clarifying aspirations and to make sure that what is planned is appropriate for the aims of that specific organization and that the various parts of the HR strategy in terms of policies and practices are integrated with each other. The elementary questions for strategic planning are "Where are we going?" and "What do we need to do to get there?" An organization needs to have a client/recipient focus. This means that the organization should identify its clients/recipients (owners, government bodies or trustees, management, employees, customers, suppliers and public at large) and their needs in order to adapt to and satisfy them. An HRM strategy and objectives therefore should be closely connected to a clear identification of its clients/recipients as well as which products/services that shall be delivered.

HR strategy

There are a multitude of schools for what an HR strategy should ideally contain. One suggestion is that an HR strategy or any kind of a strategy must have two key elements:

- strategic objectives, e.g., things the strategy is supposed to achieve, and
- a plan of action, e.g., the means by which it is intended that the objectives will be met.

The objectives should be defined in general terms of what needs to be done to satisfy the aim of the organization and the individual needs of employees. HR strategies are simply the process in bringing together people plans and programmers of activities within an overall framework, designed to deliver against organizational objectives. The process of strategy formulation is the process by which many different perspectives come to be reconciled. The image below illustrates that HRM is directly linked to the core business of a ministry with the function of providing adequate human resources.

Doing so, HRM is indirectly supporting achievement of the organizational objectives of the ministry.

The purpose of modern HRM

The purpose of modern HRM is to ensure that the organization obtains and retains the skilled, committed and well-motivated employees that it needs. Which these needs are and how they should be met in general terms should be defined in the HR strategy. The implementation of the strategy means taking steps to assess and satisfy future people needs and to enhance and develop the inherent capacities of people, their contributions, potential and employability by continuously establishing development and learning opportunities. Recruitment, placement, and training are basic HRM processes. Strengthening motivation and enhancing commitment are additional factors to achieve success. This is done by implementing policies and processes, which ascertain that people are valued and rewarded for

- (1) What they do and achieve, and for
- (2) Skills and competence and for
- (3) the willingness and ability to develop what they provide to the organization.

Values and ethics as expressed by public sector organizations usually differ only marginally when making international comparisons. Sometimes the values and ethics have a specific national or regional tilt, which is positive. Depending on the specific circumstances, it is usually necessary to ensure a diverse workforce, to provide equal opportunities and an ethical approach to managing employees, based on concern for people, rightfulness and comprehensibility, to establish various standards and norms. In its implementation, the most important factor is that

the organization in reality, and especially when it comes to managers, lives by the accepted ethics and values. Strengthening motivation and enhancing commitment by introducing and implementing policies and processes, which ascertain that people are valued and rewarded for what they do and achieve and for the levels of skills and competence and for the willingness and ability to develop that they provide to an organization, are additional factors to achieve success. An organization needs focus on creating a climate in which productive and harmonious relationships can be maintained through partnership between management and employees and where teamwork can flourish and where employees can be valued stakeholders in the organization.

The effects of HRM on productivity

So, the question is do variations in variations in HRM practices play a role in driving differences in and productivity? We find that the answer is "probably, yes", although the empirical basis for this which we survey in detail is surprisingly weak given the importance of the topic. In fact, as Severson (2010) notes in discussing management as a driver of productivity "no potential driving factor of productivity has seen a higher ratio of speculation to empirical study". We should also state in advance that in this section we focus on productivity as the key outcome. Many studies look at other outcomes such as worker turnover, absenteeism, worker perceptions, etc. These are useful, but if they have no effect on productivity then in our view they are second order generally studies use them because they have no direct evidence on productivity (e.g. Blasi et al, 2009-4). We do not focus on measures of worker wellbeing such as job satisfaction or wages. Lazear and Shaw (2008) suggest that some of the dramatic increase in wage inequality in the US, UK and other country since the late 1970s is due to HRM practices. Lemieux et al (2009) and Guadalupe and Cunat (2009a) also take this position, although the current state of the evidence is still limited. These are interesting outcomes in their own right, and may also feed through into productivity, but we are space constrained and refer the reader to the wider literature were relevant. An important issue is the correct way to econometrically estimate production functions and TFP.

The nature of the human resource management has been highlighted in its following features:

1. Inherent Part of Management: Human resource management is inherent in the process of management. This function is performed by all the managers throughout the organization rather than by the personnel department only. If a manager is to get the best of his people, he must undertake the basic responsibility of selecting people who will work under him.

2. Pervasive Function: Human Resource Management is a pervasive function of management. It is performed by all managers at various levels in the organization. It is not a responsibility that a manager can leave completely to someone else. However, he may secure advice and help in managing people from experts who have special competence in personnel management and industrial relations

3. Basic to all Functional Areas: Human Resource Management permeates all the functional areas of management such as production management, financial management, and marketing management. That is every manager from top to bottom, working in any department has to perform the personnel functions.

4. People Centered: Human Resource Management is people centered and is relevant in all types of organizations. It is concerned with all categories of personnel from top to the bottom of the organization. The broad classification of personnel in an industrial enterprise may be as follows: (i) Blue-collar workers (i.e. those working on machines and engaged in loading, unloading etc.) And white-collar workers (i.e. clerical employees), (ii) Managerial and non-managerial personnel, (iii) Professionals (such as Chartered Accountant, Company Secretary, Lawyer, etc.) and non-professionals.

5. Personnel Activities or Functions: Human Resource Management involves several functions concerned with the management of people at work. It includes manpower planning, employment, placement, training, appraisal and compensation of employees. For the performance of these activities efficiently, a separate department known as Personnel Department is created in most of the organizations.

6. Continuous Process: Human Resource Management is not a one shot function. It must be performed continuously if the organizational objectives are to be achieved smoothly.

7. Based on Human Relations: Human Resource Management is concerned with the motivation of human resources in the organization. The human beings can't be dealt with like physical factors of production. Every person has different needs, perceptions and expectations. The managers should give due attention to these factors. They require human relations skills to deal with the people at work. Human relations skills are also required in training performance appraisal, transfer and promotion of subordinates. The basic objective of human resource management is to contribute to the realization of the organizational goals. However, the specific objectives of human resource management are as follows:

- (i) To ensure effective utilization of human resources, all other organizational resources will be efficiently utilized by the human resources.
- (ii) To establish and maintain an adequate organizational structure of relationship among all the members of an organization by dividing of organization tasks into functions, positions and jobs, and by defining clearly the responsibility, accountability, authority for each job and its relation with other jobs in the organization.
- (iii) To generate maximum development of human resources within the organization by offering opportunities for advancement to employees through training and education.
- (iv) To ensure respect for human beings by providing various services and welfare facilities to the personnel.
- (v) To ensure reconciliation of individual/group goals with those of the organization in such a manner that the personnel feel a sense of commitment and loyalty towards it.
- (vi) To identify and satisfy the needs of individuals by offering various monetary and non-monetary rewards.

Human Resource Management has a place of great importance. According to Peter F. Drucker, -The proper or improper use of the different factors of production depend on the wishes of the human resources. Hence, besides other resources human resources need more development. Human resources can increase cooperation but it needs proper and efficient management to guide it. Importance of personnel management is in reality the importance of labour functions of personnel department which are indispensable to the management activity itself. Because of the following reasons human resource management holds a place of importance.

- It helps management in the preparation adoption and continuing evolution of personnel programmer and policies
- It supplies skilled workers through scientific selection process.

- It ensures maximum benefit out of the expenditure on training and development and appreciates the human assets
- It prepares workers according to the changing needs of industry and environment.
- It motivates workers and upgrades them so as to enable them to accomplish the organization goals.
- Through innovation and experimentation in the fields of personnel, it helps in reducing costs and helps in increasing productivity.
- It contributes a lot in restoring the industrial harmony and healthy employer-employee relations.
- It establishes mechanism for the administration of personnel services that are delegated to the personnel department.

HRM in public administration

Employment in public administration is in most countries different from employment in private companies and other organizations. The terms of employment, rights and duties, etc. are often regulated through laws in combination with government regulations. The room for collective or individual contracts is limited. HR issues are therefore often handled in the same way that governments regulate the activities of their subordinate institutions. Employees in public employment have a function that is special and different from other employees. Some employees in public administration execute public power in relation to individuals and organizations. Others provide services that are based on and regulated by provisions of law and government regulations. Special functions Employees in public administration are responsible before the law for their implementation of policies and provisions of law. The activities of the public institutions are governed by aims and objectives based on political decisions. The activities are regulated by laws and regulations. These characteristics form an environment for HR which is something of paradox. HRM is intended to work strategically but HRM is forced to work within the legal framework of public administration. HRM professionals within a public service organization therefore need to observe the legal framework without being limited more than necessary.

Conclusion

Human Resource Management (HRM) has changed dramatically in last two decades, with Personnel Economics now a major field in labor economics. The mark of this work is to use standard economic tools applied to the special circumstances of managing labor within companies. HRM and productivity is an exciting and lively field and has made great strides in the last two Decades. We see its future as being integrated in the general research programs of the economics of Organization and Management which are becoming a major part of modern labor economics.

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